

The Neutral Constituents of the Root and Root-bark of *Alstonia scholaris* R. Br.¹

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Alstonia scholaris R. Br. (*Apocynaceae*) (*scholaris* is Latin meaning 'belonging to schools', in allusion to the fact that the wood used to be made into blackboards) commonly known as *Chhattim* in Bengal, occurs throughout the moist region of India, specially in the west coast forests. Although this plant has been examined chemically by several investigators^{2,3} the study of its root and root-bark had not been reported earlier. Recently we have reported⁴ the occurrence of echitamine chloride as such in the root and root-bark of this plant. We now record in the present communication the isolation and characterisation of the neutral constituents, viz., α -amyrin acetate, α -amyrin, lupeol acetate, stigmasterol, β -sitosterol and campesterol or its isomer from the same plant materials, .

The petroleum ether (b.p. 60-80°) extract of the dried and powdered root-bark (2.5 kg.) of *A. scholaris* R. Br., rich in fixed oil, was made free from basic components and was chromatographed over Brockmann alumina. The chromatogram was eluted successively with solvents and solvent mixtures of increasing polarity. The petroleum ether (b.p. 40-60°) eluate fractions upon concentration gave oily residues which solidified from methanol. The crude residue, melting with a range at 150-160° was subjected to repeated chromatographic resolutions (5 times) over alumina to furnish two sharp melting crystalline solids, the one eluted out first crystallises from methanol, m.p. 221°, $[\alpha]_D^{25} +85^\circ$ (M⁺, m/e 468) and the other crystallising from the same solvent in glistening flakes. m. p. 212-13°, $[\alpha]_D^{25} +43^\circ$. They exhibited positive test for triterpene with Liebermann-Burchardt reagent. The presence of unsaturation was indicated by yellow colour with tetranitromethane. The compounds have been identified, as suggested by their m.p. and specific rotation⁵ values, with α -amyrin acetate and lupeol acetate respectively, by direct comparison with authentic samples⁶ (m.m.p., rotation and IR). Additional confirmation was obtained by hydrolysis of the acetates with 5 percent alcoholic potassium hydroxide to the corresponding

1. Part IV in the series 'Terpenoids and Related Compounds'. Part III: S. K. Talapatra, S. Sengupta and B. Talapatra, *Tetrahedron Letters*, 1968, 5963.
2. For a comprehensive review on the alkaloids of *Alstonia* species see J. E. Saxton, "Alkaloids", Vol. VIII, edited by Manske, Academic Press, New York, 1965, p. 159; A. Chatterjee, B. Mukherjee and A. B. Ray, *Tetrahedron Letters*, 1965, 3633.
3. D. Chakravarty, R. N. Chakravarti and R. Ghosh, *This Journal*, 1960, 37, 637.
4. S. K. Talapatra and B. Talapatra, *This Journal*, 1967, 44, 639.
5. The specific rotations recorded here were measured in chloroform.

alcohols^{6,7}, viz., α -amyrin, m.p. 184°, $[\alpha]_D^{20} + 88^\circ$ and lupeol, m.p. 212°, $[\alpha]_D^{20} + 28^\circ$, and converting the alcohols into α -amyrin benzoate, m.p. 194° and lupeol benzoate, m.p. 256°, $[\alpha]_D^{20} + 61^\circ$ respectively.

The solid obtained from the petroleum ether (b.p. 40-60°)-benzene (2:1) eluate fractions of the above chromatogram was rechromatographed four times to yield pure α -amyrin, crystallising from methanol in needles, m.p. 183-84°, $[\alpha]_D^{20} + 84^\circ$, identity of which was established by direct comparison with authentic sample (m.m.p. and rotation) and by converting it into the acetate which showed no depression of its m.p. upon admixture with authentic α -amyrin acetate.

The benzene-ether eluate fractions furnished a mixture of difficultly separable sterols which upon rigorous chromatography and fractional crystallisations from methanol and ethanol afforded compounds A and B both showing positive Liebermann-Burchardt test for sterol: sterol A crystallising from ethanol, m.p. 164-66°, $[\alpha]_D^{25} + 48^\circ$ (M⁺, m/e 412), was identified as stigmasterol by direct comparison with an authentic material (m.m.p. and IR) and by preparing its acetate⁷, m.p. 140-42°, $[\alpha]_D^{25} - 53^\circ$. Sterol B crystallising from methanol-chloroform mixture, m.p. 137-38°, $[\alpha]_D^{25} - 39^\circ$ (M⁺, m/e 414) could be characterised as β -sitosterol again by direct comparison with an authentic specimen (m.m.p., rotation and IR). The latter formed an acetate m.p. 129°, $[\alpha]_D^{25} - 38^\circ$ showing no depression in its melting point upon admixture with an authentic sample.

Another sterol fraction C (positive Liebermann-Burchardt test) was obtained in low yield by chromatography of the mother-liquors of the above sterols which although showed a single spot on chromatoplate melted with a range at 148-153° and could not be further purified. This solid C exhibited a peak at 3.05 μ for hydroxyl group in its IR spectrum. A high resolution mass spectrometric analysis⁸ of this material indicated it to be a mixture of three sterols: molecular ion peaks at m/e 400, 412 and 414, of which the m/e 400 peak was the most intense one assignable to the principal constituent. The above results suggest that sterol mixture C consists mainly of campesterol, C₂₈H₄₈O, (lit.⁷ m.p. 157-58°, $[\alpha]_D^{25} - 33^\circ$) or its isomer mixed with the other two congener sterols.

It needs mention in this connection that though stigmasterol and β -sitosterol isolated from this plant compared well with authentic materials, they were shown by high resolution mass spectrometry to be accompanied by trace amounts of the other two sterols. In fact, it seems that it is almost impossible to isolate these sterols in mass spectrometrically 100 per cent homogeneous and pure state whenever they

6. M. P. Cava, S. K. Talapatra, J. A. Weisbach, R. F. Raffauf, B. Douglas and J. L. Beal, *Lloydia*, 1962, 25, 222.
7. I. Heilbron and H. M. Bunbury, "Dictionary of Organic Compounds," Eyre & Spottiswoode, London, 1953.
8. All mass spectral measurements were made with AEI. MS-9 mass spectrometer operating at 70 e. v. and the compounds exhibited expected mass fragmentation pattern.

co-occur in nature. The root of *A. scholaris* upon processing in a similar manner furnished α -amyrin acetate, lupeol acetate, β -sitosterol and stigmasterol but in poor yield.

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